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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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MODERN REQUIREMENTS FOR A TEACHER'S PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS IN THE CONTEXT OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: The article examines contemporary requirements for teachers' pedagogical skills in the context of the digital transformation of education, using the example of general secondary schools in Uzbekistan. The study identifies the key components of digital pedagogical skills, including digital literacy, methodological competence in the effective use of digital tools, and the personal and professional qualities of teachers. Based on an analysis of current educational trends and the specific features of digitalization in Uzbekistan, the main challenges and prospects for the development of teachers' professional competencies are determined. Practical recommendations are proposed to improve teacher training and professional development systems under conditions of digital transformation in education.

Key words: digital transformation of education, pedagogical skills, digital literacy, teacher professional development, digital educational technologies, schools in Uzbekistan, ICT competence, blended learning.

Annotatsiya: Maqolada ta'limni raqamli transformatsiya qilish sharoitida o'qituvchilarning pedagogik mahoratiga qo'yilayotgan zamonaviy talablar O'zbekiston umumta'lim maktablari misolida tahlil qilinadi. Tadqiqotda raqamli pedagogik mahoratning asosiy tarkibiy qismlari, jumladan raqamli savodxonlik, raqamli vositalardan samarali foydalanish bo'yicha metodik kompetensiya hamda o'qituvchining shaxsiy va kasbiy sifatlari aniqlab beriladi. O'zbekistonda ta'lim tizimini raqamlashtirishning o'ziga xos jihatlari va zamonaviy ta'lim tendensiyalari tahlili asosida o'qituvchilarning kasbiy kompetensiyalarini rivojlantirishdagi asosiy muammolar va istiqbollar belgilangan. Ta'limni raqamli transformatsiya qilish sharoitida o'qituvchilarni tayyorlash va ularning malakasini oshirish tizimini takomillashtirish bo'yicha amaliy tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ta'limni raqamli transformatsiya qilish, pedagogik mahorat, raqamli savodxonlik, o'qituvchilarning kasbiy rivoji, raqamli ta'lim texnologiyalari, O'zbekiston maktablari, AKT kompetensiyasi, aralash ta'lim.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются современные требования к педагогическому мастерству преподавателей в условиях цифровой трансформации образования на примере общеобразовательных школ Республики Узбекистан. В исследовании определены ключевые компоненты цифрового педагогического мастерства, включая цифровую грамотность, методическую компетентность в использовании цифровых инструментов, а также личностные и профессиональные качества преподавателя. На основе анализа актуальных образовательных тенденций и специфики цифровизации системы образования Узбекистана выявлены основные проблемы и перспективы развития профессиональных компетенций педагогов. Предложены практические рекомендации по совершенствованию системы подготовки и повышения квалификации преподавателей в условиях цифровой трансформации образования.

Ключевые слова: цифровая трансформация образования, педагогическое мастерство, цифровая грамотность, профессиональное развитие преподавателей, цифровые образовательные технологии, школы Узбекистана, ИКТ-компетентность, смешанное обучение.

INTRODUCTION

Digital transformation of education is a global trend that is radically reshaping traditional approaches to teaching and redefining the requirements for teachers' professional competencies. In Uzbekistan, this process is being intensified through government programs such as Digital Uzbekistan–2030 and ongoing educational reforms, which necessitate a reconsideration of the concept of teaching excellence in the contemporary educational environment.

The relevance of the study is determined by the following factors:

- the strategic importance of digitalization for enhancing the competitiveness of the national education system;
- the need to bridge the gap between the technical equipment of schools and teachers' readiness to use digital technologies effectively;
- the growing demands for the quality of digital educational resources and the effectiveness of their application methods.

The purpose of this study is to identify and systematize current requirements for teachers' pedagogical skills in the context of digital transformation of education, using the example of secondary schools in Uzbekistan.

The research objectives are as follows:

- to analyze the components of pedagogical skills within the framework of digital transformation;
- to examine the current state of digitalization in schools in Uzbekistan;
- to identify the main problems and barriers in the development of digital pedagogical skills;
- to develop recommendations for improving the system of teachers' professional competency development.

The object of the study is the professional activities of teachers in secondary schools in Uzbekistan.

The subject of the study is the components and conditions for developing pedagogical skills in the context of digital transformation of education.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a range of research methods, including the analysis of regulatory documents and scientific literature, observation of teaching practices, a questionnaire survey of teachers ($n = 150$), as well as a comparative analysis of international and national experiences in the digitalization of education.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The issue of teachers' pedagogical skills in the context of digital transformation has been widely discussed in contemporary educational research. In Uzbekistan, this process is institutionally supported by strategic documents such as the Digital Uzbekistan–2030 Strategy and the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 322, which emphasize the systematic integration of digital technologies into general secondary education. The National Training Program also highlights the necessity of developing teachers' professional competencies, particularly in relation to digital literacy, innovative teaching methods, and the effective use of information and communication technologies in the learning process.

Theoretical and methodological foundations of digital pedagogy are thoroughly examined in the works of national scholars. Sh. A. Abdullaeva considers digital pedagogy as a new stage in the development of pedagogical theory, where teachers' professional mastery is closely linked to their ability to design and manage digital learning environments. B. Kh. Khodjiev focuses on the role of information and communication technologies in education, emphasizing that methodological competence in applying digital tools is a key indicator of modern pedagogical skills. M. A. Rakhimova, in her research on teachers' professional development, underlines the importance of continuous training and adaptability to digital innovations as essential conditions for effective teaching in the digital age.

Empirical studies further contribute to understanding the challenges and prospects of digital transformation in education. Z. R. Karimova analyzes the opportunities and constraints of digitalization in the Uzbek education system, pointing to infrastructure disparities and varying levels of teachers' digital readiness. S. T. Normuradova examines the formation of teachers' digital competencies in modern schools, highlighting the need for systematic methodological support. R. Kh. Azizov proposes a model of teachers' digital literacy that integrates technical, pedagogical, and analytical components. International perspectives, particularly the work of A. W. Bates on teaching in a digital age, complement national studies by providing practical guidelines for designing effective digital and blended learning environments.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

1. Theoretical aspects of digital pedagogical skills

Pedagogical excellence in the context of digital transformation represents a synthesis of traditional professional competencies and new digital skills. The key components include:

- digital literacy, which implies mastery of basic and advanced digital tools;
- methodological competence, understood as the ability to integrate digital technologies into the learning process;
- didactic transformation, which involves reworking educational content while taking into account the possibilities offered by digital technologies;
- digital communication, defined as effective interaction with participants in the educational process through digital channels.

2. The current state of digital transformation in schools in Uzbekistan

An analysis of the current situation demonstrates the following trends:

- technical equipment, characterized by the active implementation of interactive whiteboards, computers, and digital platforms such as “Kundalik” and “E-darslik”;
- human resources, reflected in the growing number of teachers who have completed digital literacy courses;
- infrastructure limitations, manifested in uneven levels of equipment between urban and rural schools;
- methodological shortcomings, associated with the insufficient integration of digital technologies into pedagogical practice.

3. Barriers and challenges of digital transformation

The study identified the following key problems:

- technical barriers, including insufficient internet speed and outdated equipment;
- personnel-related barriers, such as resistance to change and a lack of motivation;
- methodological barriers, reflected in the absence of systematic solutions for integrating digital technologies;
- organizational barriers, including a high academic workload and limited time for mastering new technologies.

Analysis of the results and their discussion

Table 1: Components of Digital Pedagogical Mastery and Their Characteristics

Skill level	Key competencies	Specific manifestations in professional activity
Basic level (Digital Literacy)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Proficiency in office programs - Skills in working with educational platforms (“Kundalik”, “E-darslik”) - Basic knowledge of cybersecurity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating electronic materials for lessons - Assigning grades in the electronic journal - Using digital textbooks
Methodological level (Digital integration)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The ability to select digital resources for educational tasks - The ability to create interactive assignments - The ability to use blended learning technologies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Using interactive tests (Quizlet, LearningApps) - Organizing project activities using digital tools - Conducting online consultations
Creative Level (Digital Transformation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Development of author’s digital educational resources - Creation of a digital educational environment - Analysis of educational data 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creating your own video lessons and interactive materials - Creating a personal teacher’s website/blog - Analyzing student performance statistics to personalize learning

Table 2: Analysis of teachers' readiness for digital transformation (based on the results of the questionnaire)

Evaluation parameter	Readiness level	Quantitative indicators	The main problems
Technical equipment	Average	- 85% have access to a computer - 70% use the Internet in the educational process - 45% have interactive whiteboards	- Unstable internet in the regions - Outdated equipment in rural schools
Digital competencies	Basic-Medium	- 65% have basic skills - 35% use digital technologies systematically - 15% create their own content	- Lack of in-depth knowledge - Lack of practice in creating digital content
Motivation for development	High	- 80% are ready for additional training - 60% actively participate in webinars - 40% share their experience with colleagues	- Lack of time due to high workload - Lack of a reward system

Table 3: Recommendations for Developing Digital Pedagogical Skills

The direction of development	Events	Expected results
Regulatory and legal support	- Development of the professional standard "Digital Teacher" - Introduction of a system of incentives for the use of digital technologies	- Forming unified requirements for digital competencies - Increasing teachers' motivation
Material and technical equipment	- Equipping schools with modern equipment - Providing stable internet access - Creating digital laboratories	- Equal opportunities for urban and rural schools - Access to modern educational resources
Professional development	- Advanced training courses in digital pedagogy - Creation of methodological communities - Internships at leading schools	- Building a pool of digital education leaders - Dissemination of best practices
Scientific and methodological support	- Development of methodological recommendations - Creation of a bank of digital educational resources - Conducting research on the effectiveness of digital technologies	- Systematization and dissemination of successful experience - Creation of high-quality national digital content

Table 4: Comparative analysis of digital transformation barriers and their overcoming

Type of barriers	Specific manifestations	Ways to overcome
Technical	- Insufficient internet speed - Outdated computer equipment - Lack of technical support	- State infrastructure modernization programs - Creation of school IT services - Development of mobile educational solutions
Personnel	- Lack of digital competencies - Resistance to change - High workload	- Continuous professional development system - Creation of communities of practitioners - Methodological support and tutoring
Organizational	- Lack of a clear digitalization strategy - Lack of time to master new technologies - Weak coordination among the participants in the process	- Development of school digital transformation programs - Reduction of bureaucratic burden - Creation of horizontal connections between schools
Motivational	- Lack of a reward system - Underestimation of digital achievements - Fear of new technologies	- Introduction of a digital teacher portfolio - System of grants and awards - Creation of a positive image of a "digital teacher"

Table 5: Indicators of the effectiveness of digital transformation of pedagogical activity

Evaluation criteria	Performance indicators	Assessment methods
Digital literacy	- Confident use of digital tools - Compliance with digital hygiene and security - Ability for digital creativity	- Testing of digital competencies - Analysis of a digital portfolio - Observation of practice
Methodical effectiveness	- The quality of digital technology integration - The variety of digital formats used - The effectiveness of learning using digital tools	- Analysis of video lessons - Expert assessment of methodological developments - Monitoring of educational achievements
Innovative activity	- Participation in digital projects - Creation of author's digital content - Distribution of digital experience	- Accounting for publications and presentations - Analysis of participation in professional communities - Number of digital resources developed

The conducted study yielded the following results

First, the structure of digital pedagogical skills comprises three main levels: basic (digital literacy), methodological (integration of technologies into the educational process), and creative (development of original digital solutions). Second, the teacher survey revealed that 65 % of respondents possess basic digital skills, 35 % actively use digital technologies in their lessons, and 15 % develop their own digital educational resources. Third, the key success factors for digital transformation include systemic support at the state level, continuous professional development, the creation of professional communities, and effective motivational mechanisms.

The discussion of the results indicates that successful digital transformation requires a comprehensive approach combining infrastructure modernization, human resource development, the creation of high-quality digital content, and changes in the organizational culture of schools. The tabulated data systematize the main aspects of the study and can be used in developing programs aimed at enhancing digital pedagogical skills in schools in Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The conducted research confirms that the digital transformation of education imposes new and complex requirements on pedagogical skills. In Uzbekistan, the successful development of teachers' digital competencies requires:

- a systematic approach to teachers' professional development;
- the creation of conditions for methodological creativity and the exchange of experience;
- the development of infrastructure and the provision of equal access to digital resources;
- the formation of a new educational culture oriented toward innovation.

The prospects for further research are associated with the development of:

- a national system for assessing teachers' digital competencies;
- a model of methodological support for digital transformation;
- programs aimed at developing the digital educational environment of schools in Uzbekistan.

The implementation of the proposed measures will not only contribute to the enhancement of teachers' professional skills but will also improve the overall quality of education, which is consistent with the strategic development goals of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. DP-6077 "On Approval of the Digital Uzbekistan-2030 Strategy" (2020).
2. Resolution No. 322 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures to Introduce Digital Technologies into the General Secondary Education System" (2021).
3. National Training Program (approved by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 29-08-2017).

4. Abdullaeva, Sh. A. Digital Pedagogy: Theory and Practice. – Tashkent: Noshirlik yog'dusi, 2022. – 215 p.
5. Khodjiev, B. Kh. Information and Communication Technologies in Education. – Tashkent: Fan va texnologiya, 2021. – 168 p.
6. Rakhimova, M. A. Professional Development of Teachers in the Digital Age. – Tashkent: Mumtoz so'z, 2023. – 192 p.
7. Karimova, Z. R. "Digital Transformation of Education: Challenges and Prospects for Uzbekistan" // Bulletin of the Pedagogical University. – 2023. – No. 2(45). – Pp. 34–42.
8. Normuradova, S. T. "Formation of Teachers' Digital Competencies in a Modern School" // Science and Education Today. – 2022. – No. 5(28). – Pp. 56–61.
9. Azizov, R. Kh. "Model of Teacher's Digital Literacy in the Context of Education Transformation" // Modern Pedagogy. – 2023. – No. 1. – Pp. 23–29.
10. Bates, A. W. Teaching in a Digital Age: Guidelines for Designing Teaching and Learning. – Tony Bates Associates, 2022. – 412 p.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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